

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART VIII. OXIDATION WITH CHLORAMINE-T.

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Hydroquinone, quinhydrone, hydrazine hydrochloride, potassium iodide, sodium bisulphite and sodium nitrite have been determined by titrating them potentiometrically at 15° against chloramine-T, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode.

Noil (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1924, 48, 845) described the use of chloramine-T *i.e.*, the sodium compound of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide, as a reagent for oxidation purposes. The solid salt has the composition

In solution it behaves like a stable hypochlorite

This reagent is finding increasing use in place of sodium hypochlorite. It has the advantage that its aqueous solution is stable in air and shows only slight deterioration over long periods when kept in a stoppered bottle; moreover, as alkali is absent, there is no risk of formation of chlorates, which lead to side-reactions.

This reacts in acid solution with potassium iodide to liberate iodine

and this reaction is useful for its standardisation.

Rupp (*Pharm. Zentr.*, 1925, 66, 33) used chloramine-T for the determination of trivalent antimony, and later for the titration of stannous tin (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1928, 73, 51).

Tomicek and Sucharda (*Chem. Abs.*, 1932, 26, 1210) used it as a reagent for the potentiometric determination of trivalent arsenic and antimony; bivalent tin and iron and the ferrocyanide and iodide ions; and for the visual titration of trivalent arsenic and antimony, using methyl red as indicator.

Komarovskii, Filonova and Kogenman (*J. Appl. Chem. Russia*, 1933, 6, 742; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, 96, 321) have shown that chloramine-T can be used as a volumetric reagent to replace the more expensive iodine and the

less stable hypochlorite in the estimation of ferrocyanide, hydrazine and hypophosphite.

In the volumetric estimations a crystal of potassium iodide and a few c.c. of starch solution are added and the solution titrated with chloramine-T. The presence of a slight excess of the reagent (end-point) is shown by the liberation of iodine and the appearance of the blue colour of starch iodide.

Chloramine-T oxidises hydroquinone, quinhydrone, hydrazine hydrochloride, potassium iodide, sodium bisulphite and sodium nitrite. The reactions are represented by the following equations :—

These reactions have been utilised in the quantitative determination of these substances by the potentiometric method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oxidation-reduction electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil immersed in the solution to be titrated, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The cell was placed in a water-bath, the temperature of which was kept at 15°. The e.m.f. of the cell was read on a potentiometer.

A known weight of the substance was dissolved in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid except in case of nitrite. The solution was titrated potentiometrically against standard chloramine-T. The mixture was kept stirred very thoroughly with a mechanical stirrer.

In the case of sodium nitrite acetic acid was used. A known volume of a standard solution of chloramine-T was taken in the titration vessel, acidified with acetic acid and titrated against sodium nitrite solution,

The titrations of potassium iodide were conducted in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

The potentiometric readings were recorded after the addition of the reagent, when the potential acquired a steady value. A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration as typical of the set is recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

Titration of 0.1066 g. of hydroquinone mixed with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, against chloramine-T ($M/20$).

Chloramine-T.	E.M.F.	E/C . (m. volt/c.c.)	Chloramine-T.	E.M.F.	E/C . (m. volt/c.c.)
0.00 c.c.	0.295 volts.		19.20 c.c.	0.479 volts.	
2.00	0.381	43	19.25	0.502	460
5.00	0.390	3	19.30	0.567	1300
8.00	0.396	2	19.35	0.655	1760 (Maximum)
10.00	0.400	2			900
12.00	0.405	3	19.40	0.700	210
14.00	0.410	3	19.50	0.721	120
16.00	0.416	3	19.70	0.745	63
17.00	0.421	5	20.00	0.764	49
17.80	0.426	8	21.00	0.812	29
18.30	0.435	18	22.00	0.831	17
18.80	0.448	26	24.00	0.864	12
19.00	0.460	60	27.00	0.900	7
19.10	0.468	80	30.00	0.920	4
		110	34.00	0.937	

D I S C U S S I O N .

These titrations, except in the case of hydrazine hydrochloride, show that with the addition of the standard chloramine-T, the E.M.F. rose steadily till the equivalence-point. In the case of hydrazine hydrochloride, on first few additions of the titrant, the E.M.F. remained constant. This was followed by a steady rise till the equivalence-point on further addition of the reagent. At the equivalence-point there was a sharp jump in potential, followed by a steady rise in each case.

In the case of sodium nitrite, since it was used as the titrant, the E.M.F. decreased steadily till the equivalence-point. At the equivalence-point there was a sharp break in E.M.F. This was followed by a steady decrease in potential.

From the volume of chloramine-T required in each case, corresponding to the equivalence-point, the amount of the substance was calculated. In the following table the values are compared with the amounts of the substance taken.

TABLE II.

Hydroquinone.		Quinhydrone.		Hydrazine hydrochloride.	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.1066 g.	0.1064 g.	0.1152 g.	0.1150 g.	0.0591 g.	0.0590 g.
0.1517	0.1513	0.2048	0.2045	0.0996	0.0990
0.2171	0.2168	0.2836	0.2835	0.1465	0.1462
0.2583	0.2580	0.3986	0.3981	0.1772	0.1768
0.3549	0.3543	0.4890	0.4884	0.2001	0.1995
				0.2416	0.2409
Sodium bisulphite.		Potassium iodide.		Sodium nitrite.	
0.0321 g.	0.0320 g.	0.0415 g.	0.0415 g.	0.0345 g.	0.0345 g.
0.0477	0.0477	0.0830	0.0830	0.0428	0.0428
0.0801	0.0800	0.1660	0.1660	0.0518	0.0518
0.1285	0.1283	0.2490	0.2490	0.0690	0.0690
0.1749	0.1746	0.3320	0.3320	0.1035	0.1035
				0.1380	0.1380

These results show that hydroquinone, quinhydrone, hydrazine hydrochloride, potassium iodide, sodium bisulphite and sodium nitrite can be potentiometrically determined by using chloramine-T as the oxidising agent.

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